

Citrus Aurantifolia Leaves Extract As A Green Corrosion Inhibitor For Aluminium Metal In Hydrochloric Acid Media

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Abstract— The corrosion inhibition of aluminum metal in hydrochloric acid was studied at varying Citrus aurantifolium leaves extract concentration, temperature and corrodent (HCl) concentration for an immersion period of 4 hours using weight loss technique. The nature of interaction of the plant extract with the aluminum coupon surface morphology was studied using SEM technique. The results obtained showed that an increase in the inhibition efficiency of the plant extract was obtained with increase in its concentration, decrease in HCl concentration and that of temperature. The process of the inhibition is adjured to be spontaneous and feasible due to the evaluated thermodynamic parameters (ΔG and ΔH). The SEM and ΔG parameters prove the process to be through physical adsorption. The plant Citrus aurantifolium leaves extract has been established to be a good inhibitor of aluminum in hydrochloric acid solution.

Keywords- Phytochemical, Corrosion study, Inhibition efficiency, Adsorption

I. INTRODUCTION

According to IUPAC, corrosion is an irreversible surface reaction of a material and its surrounding that leads to the consumption of the material. As a result, corrosion can be seen as the reverse of metal extraction (Zhang and Hua, 2010). Also, to corrosion Engineers, they refer to corrosion mainly as the oxidation of metal by chemical or electrochemical process (Roberge, 2008).

Metals and their alloys are used every day in industries as part of machineries and also reaction vessels. The acids used for cleaning, descaling and pickling those metallic materials however, attack and consequently corrode the material (Abiola and James, 2010).

Aluminum is the second most used metals in manufacturing industries commonly used as reaction vessels, valves and chemical battery parts (Abiola et al., 2007). Aluminum is of great technological importance due to its low cost, light weight and high thermal and electrical conductivity (Ayuba et al., 2018). Aluminum is highly electropositive and resistant to corrosion to some extent, this is as a result of formation of compact, adherent and protective oxide film on its surface. Owing to this properties aluminum is widely used in many industries for production of wires, sheets, tubes and machineries parts (Prabakaran et al., 2018).

Lots of efforts have been made, aiming at protecting aluminum surface in an aggressive or corrosive medium against its corrosion. In recent years, the most common approach that has been in use is the addition of inhibitors to retard or hinder the corrosion process (Deng and Li, 2012).

Nowadays, plant extracts are used as viable alternative for corrosion inhibition. The bioactive compounds in the plant act

as a barrier between the corrosive media and the metal surface there by inhibiting the corrosion of the metal. (Kamarska, 2023).

II. METHODOLOGY

A. PREPARATION OF THE ALUMINUM COUPON

Composition of the aluminum sheet was analyzed using energy dispersive x-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (ED-XRF). The coupons were cut with scissors into 2 by 3 cm for the weight loss analysis and scanning electron microscopy. The coupons were polished with abrasive paper, degreased by washing with ethanol and cleaned with acetone before use (Ayuba and Abdullateef, 2021).

B. PLANT SAMPLE COLLECTION AND PREPARATION

Fresh leaves of Citrus aurantifolia were obtained and authenticated at Plant Science department Bayero University Kano herbarium with the given number BUKHAN 0113. The leaves were then washed and dried in shade at room temperature then ground to powder form and then sieved.

300g of the powdered sample was then weighed and soaked with 1500ml of 98% ethanol and left for two weeks while shaking periodically. The extract was then filtered using Whatman paper and concentrated using rotary evaporator. The resulting filtrate was then allowed to evaporate to dryness at room temperature (Ayuba and Mustapha, 2013).

C. WEIGHT LOSS ANALYSIS

Four pieces of aluminum coupons were pre-weighted and then immersed in four different beakers containing 30cm³ of the

prepared corroder solution of 0.3M containing 0.00g/L, 0.20g/L, 0.40g/L and 0.60g/L plant extract differently. The coupons were removed after every hour cleaned, from all corrosion products and reweighed for a total four hours period. The process was carried out at 303K, 313K and 323K. The whole process was repeated for 0.60M and 0.90M acid concentration while varying the temperature.

From the weight loss result data obtained, inhibition efficiency (IE), surface coverage (Θ) and corrosion rate (CR) were calculated using equation 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3 respectively (Eddy et al., 2009).

$$IE = \left(1 - \frac{W_1}{W_2}\right) \times 100 \quad (3.1)$$

$$(\theta) = 1 - \frac{W_1}{W_2} \quad (3.2)$$

$$CR = \frac{W}{At} \quad (3.3)$$

Where W1 and W2 are the weight loss of the aluminum coupons in the presence and absence of the inhibitor respectively, IE is the inhibition efficiency (%), Θ is the surface coverage, CR is the corrosion rate (mg/h/cm²), A is the area of the aluminum coupon (cm²), t is time (h) and W is weight loss of aluminum coupon for time, t.

D. SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPY (SEM) ANALYSIS

The surface morphologies of fresh aluminum coupon, that immersed in a 0.3M HCl solution and that immersed in different concentration of Citrus aurantiolia extract as the inhibitor (0.20g/L, 0.40g/L and 0.60g/L) for four hours were scanned using SEM (JSM-6360LV, JEOL, Tokyo, Japan) at an accelerating voltage of 15 kV and 1500 magnification (Kamarska 2023).

E. THERMODYNAMIC STUDIES

Thermodynamic parameters including the Gibb's free energy change of adsorption (ΔG_{ads}), enthalpy change (ΔH) and entropy change (ΔS) were calculated from the weight loss data obtained. The thermodynamic data were evaluated at different acid concentrations, inhibitor concentrations and temperatures.

1) Equilibrium Constant Kads

The values for the equilibrium constant (Kads) at different acid concentrations, inhibitor concentrations and temperatures were calculated using the relation in equation 3.4.

$$K_{ads} = \frac{\theta}{C(1-\theta)} \quad (3.4)$$

Where Kads is the equilibrium constant of adsorption, θ is the degree of surface coverage of the aluminum metal and C is the concentration of the inhibitors (Zhang and Hua 2009).

2) Gibbs Free Energy Change of Adsorption ΔG

The Gibbs free energy change of adsorption of the plant extract on the aluminum surface values was also determined using equation 3.5 (Nwosu et al, 2018):

$$\Delta G_{ads} = -RT \ln(55.5K_{ads}) \quad (3.5)$$

3) Enthalpy change (ΔH) and Entropy change (ΔS)

The enthalpy changes also at different acid and inhibitor concentrations and at different temperatures were calculated using the equation 3.6 (Ating et al., 2010):

$$\log \frac{CR}{T} = \left[\log \left(\frac{R}{Nh} \right) + \frac{\Delta S}{2.303R} \right] - \frac{\Delta H}{2.303RT} \quad (3.6)$$

Where CR is the corrosion rate, h is the Planck's constant (6.62607x10⁻³⁴ Js), N is the Avogadro's number (6.02214x10²³ mol⁻¹), T is the absolute temperature, R is the universal gas constant, ΔH is the enthalpy of activation. A plot of Log (CR/T) as a function of 1/T gives a straight line with a slope of $\left(\frac{-\Delta H}{2.303R} \right)$ from which the values of ΔH was calculated by rearranging the relation. (Yadav et al, 2018).

III. RESULTS

1) Weight Loss Analysis Result

The Inhibition efficiency (IE), Surface coverage (Θ) and corrosion rate (CR) of the aluminum coupons in different corroder concentration, plant extract concentration as well as different temperatures were calculated using equation 3.1, 3.2, and 3.3 respectively by utilizing the data from weight loss analysis. The result is presented in the table 1:

Table 1: Values of Inhibition Efficiency, Surface Coverage and Corrosion Rate

Temp	Inhibitor (g/L)	HCl Concentration								
		0.30M		0.60M		0.90M				
		IE (%)	Θ	CR (g/h/cm ²)	IE (%)	Θ	CR (g/h/cm ²)	IE (%)	Θ	CR (g/h/cm ²)
303K	Blank	-	-	0.011	-	-	0.026	-	-	0.041
	0.20	31.54	0.255	0.008	30.65	0.336	0.017	25.25	0.312	0.028
	0.40	49.79	0.448	0.006	39.56	0.396	0.016	32.45	0.325	0.027
	0.60	72.39	0.654	0.004	61.59	0.616	0.010	45.81	0.458	0.022
313K	Blank	-	-	0.014	-	-	0.027	-	-	0.041
	0.20	23.28	0.233	0.011	19.13	0.191	0.022	17.87	0.239	0.031
	0.40	43.84	0.438	0.008	35.24	0.352	0.017	30.35	0.303	0.029
	0.60	48.50	0.485	0.007	46.13	0.461	0.015	35.93	0.359	0.026
323K	Blank	-	-	0.016	-	-	0.030	-	-	0.041
	0.20	21.54	0.215	0.013	18.43	0.184	0.024	14.92	0.149	0.035
	0.40	35.52	0.355	0.011	21.49	0.215	0.023	16.16	0.162	0.034
	0.60	39.78	0.398	0.010	32.27	0.323	0.020	19.65	0.196	0.033

2) Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

The scanned micrographs of fresh aluminum coupon, that immersed in a 0.3M HCl solution and that immersed in different concentration of Citrus aurantiolia extract as the inhibitor (0.20g/L, 0.40g/L and 0.60g/L) for four hours were scanned using SEM (JSM-6360LV, JEOL, Tokyo, Japan) at an accelerating voltage of 15 kV and 1500 magnification are presented in figure 1-5 below.

Figure 1: Micrograph for Fresh (Uncorroded) Coupon

Figure 2: Micrograph for Corroded Coupon in 0.3M acid

Figure 3: Micrograph of the Coupon in 0.20g/L Inhibitor

Figure 4: Micrograph of the Coupon in 0.40g/L Inhibitor

Fig 5: Micrograph of the Coupon in 0.60g/L Inhibitor

3) Thermodynamic Result

The results obtained from the calculation of equilibrium constant (K_{ads}), Gibbs free energy change (ΔG) and enthalpy change (ΔH) at different inhibitor concentrations and different acid concentration for various temperatures are presented in table 2, 3 and 4 below:

Table 2: K_{ads}

	HCl Concentration(M)								
	0.3			0.6			0.9		
Temp(K)	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.2	0.4	0.6
303	1.715	2.028	3.148	2.535	1.636	2.672	2.273	1.201	1.409
313	1.517	1.951	1.570	1.183	1.361	1.427	1.568	1.089	0.935
323	1.373	1.377	1.101	1.129	0.684	0.794	0.877	0.482	0.407

Table 3: Change in Gibbs Free Energy (ΔG) (kJ/mol) Values obtained

Temp(K)	HCl Concentration(M)								
	0.3			0.6			0.9		
	Inhibitor concentration(g/L)			Inhibitor concentration(g/L)			Inhibitor concentration(g/L)		
303	-11.48	-11.90	-13.01	-12.46	-11.36	-12.59	-12.19	-10.58	-10.98
313	11.54	-12.19	-11.63	-10.89	-11.25	-11.38	-11.62	-10.67	-10.28
323	-11.64	-11.65	-11.04	-11.11	-9.77	-10.17	-10.43	-8.82	-8.37

Table 4: Enthalpy change (ΔH), at various HCl and Inhibitor concentration

inhibitor g/L	Enthalpy change (ΔH), kJ/mol		
	0.30M	0.60M	0.90M
0.20	-9.06	-33.20	-38.63
0.40	-15.60	-35.25	-36.84
0.60	-42.88	-49.37	-50.27

IV. DISCUSSION

A. EFFECT OF ACID CONCENTRATION ON WEIGHT LOSS

The effect of varying acid concentration on the weight loss of aluminum has been studied at 0.30M, 0.60M and 0.90M HCl concentrations across various inhibitor concentrations(0.00g/L, 0.20g/L, 0.40g/L and 0.60g/L) and temperatures(303K, 313K and 323K). It can be observed from the result presented in table 1 that the increase in the acid concentration leads to the increase in corrosion rate. The corrosion rate was found to increase from 0.0114g/h/cm² at 0.30M acid concentration to 0.0261g/h/cm²

at 0.60M and then to 0.0405g/h/cm² at 0.90M. This shows that the higher the concentration of the acid the higher the weight loss of aluminum which is in accordance with the general rule guiding the rate of chemical reactions which stated that the chemical reaction increases with increasing concentration (Mat Satar et al, 2011).

So also, the increasing acid concentration was found to decrease the inhibition efficiency. This trend can be seen also in table 1. At 303K for instance, while the inhibitor concentration was kept at 0.20g/L, the inhibition efficiency was found to decrease from 31.54% at 0.30M acid concentration to 30.65% and 25.25% at 0.60M and 0.90M acid concentrations respectively. This can be explained that the increase in corrodent concentration has taken over the inhibition process of the inhibitor molecules (Kamarska, 2023).

B. EFFECT OF INHIBITOR CONCENTRATION ON WEIGHT LOSS

The effect of Citrus aurantifolia leaves extract as the inhibitor on corrosion rate and inhibition efficiency was also examined. The effect was studied for various extract concentrations (0.20g/L, 0.40g/L and 0.60g/L) at varying acid concentration and temperatures.

The increasing inhibitor concentration was found to increase the inhibition efficiency of the aluminum corrosion. This was also depicted in table 1. From table, the inhibition efficiency at 0.20g/L inhibitor was 31.54%, but the inhibition efficiency enhanced to 49.74% and 72.39% by increasing the inhibitor concentration to 0.40g/L and 0.60g/L respectively. This behavior of increase in inhibition efficiency with increasing inhibitor concentration could be attributed to the increase in surface coverage of the adsorbed inhibitor molecules on the aluminum surface thereby creating more barrier for mass and charge transfer between the acid and the metal and hence isolating the metal from further attack of the corrosive environment (Hachelef et l., 2016).

On the other hand, the inhibitor concentration was also found to suppress corrosion rate. This can be seen from table 1 also. The corrosion rate was 0.0114g/h/cm² initially, while on the addition of the inhibitor of 0.20g/L concentration, the corrosion rate reduced to 0.0085g/h/cm². This value also decreases further to 0.0063g/h/cm² and 0.0039g/h/cm² at the inhibitor concentration of 0.40g/L and 0.60g/L respectively. This suggest that the accumulation of the Citrus aurantifolia leaves extract molecules onto the aluminum surface reduces direct contact of the metal by locking the active sites in which direct acid attack proceed and protect the aluminum from corrosion (Al-Turkustani and Al-Solmi, 2011).

C. EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON WEIGHT LOSS

The temperature effect on the corrosion rate and inhibition efficiency were all examined. Temperatures of 303K, 313K and 323K were used to investigate these effects at various acid and inhibitor concentrations. The temperature increase was found to increase the corrosion rate as seen in table 1. From the result of corrosion rate variation with temperature at 0.3M HCl concentration, the corrosion rate was found to increase from 0.0114g/h/cm² at 303k to 0.0142g/h/cm² and 0.0163g/h/cm² at

313K and 323K respectively. This also can be attributed to the increase in the mobility of the corrodent molecules making them finding their way to the metal surface and also the desorption of the inhibitor-metal layer allowing easy passage of the acid to the metal surface (Ashassi-Sorkhabi et al., 2005).

The temperature also suppresses the inhibition efficiency effect. These was also shown in table 1. From the inhibition efficiency variation with temperature at 0.3M HCl concentration, the inhibition efficiency was 31.54% initially at 303K. But with increase in temperature to 313K, the inhibition efficiency decreased to 23.28% and went further to decrease to 21.54% at 323K. This can be due to decreasing surfactant adsorption at higher temperatures and this can further suggest that physical adsorption may be the type of adsorption of the inhibitor on the metal surface (Abd El Rehim et al, 2001). The influence may also come from the weakening of electrostatic adsorption on the metal surface and the aggravation of desorption of the inhibitor molecule from the metal surface when the temperature increases (Zhao et al, 2017).

D. SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPY ANALYSIS (SEM)

The surface of aluminum coupon was morphologically characterized by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) for fresh aluminum coupon, corroded aluminum in 0.30M HCl concentration and inhibited aluminum coupons in different inhibitor concentrations (0,20g/L, 0.40g/L and 0.60g/L) all at 303K for a period of 4 hours. The images obtained are shown in figure 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5.

The morphology of fresh aluminum coupon in figure 1 can be seen maintain a smooth surface which is the initial morphology before corrosion process take place. By inserting the aluminum coupon in corrosive environment of 0.30M HCl concentration, a micrograph presented in figure 2 was obtained which shows presence of pits and cracks indicating damage and dissolution of aluminum metal in contact with the corrosive HCl medium (Zhao et al, 2017). Figure 3, 4 and 5 are the micrographs of the aluminum coupons in 0.20g/L, 0.40g/L and 0.60g/L concentration of Citrus aurantifolia leaves extract respectively. The micrographs can be observed to have a less distorted morphology by the acid attack and there is clear formation of adsorption layer at the aluminum surface which can be attributed to the adsorption of Citrus aurantifolia leaves extract molecules (Fares et al, 2012; Chaudhary and Tak, 2022; Al-Haj-Ali et al, 2014).

E. THERMODYNAMIC STUDIES

1) Equilibrium Constant (K_{ads})

The equilibrium constant of adsorption as calculated and presented in Table 2. The equilibrium constant values were found to all decrease with increasing temperature. From the table, at 0.3M HCl concentration and 0.20g/L inhibitor concentration, the K_{ads} decrease from 1.715 at 303K to 1.517 at 313K and 1.377 at 323K. The highest equilibrium constant was found at 0.3M HCl concentration, 0.60g/L inhibitor concentration and at 303K temperature which was the exact parameters that yield the highest inhibition efficiency. This

proved that inhibition efficiency is associated with equilibrium constant.

The decrease in the equilibrium constant values is due to larger surface energy that could sufficiently release and desorb the adsorbed molecules and hinder or impede the adsorption of inhibitor and mediator on the metal surface. (Fares et al., 2012).

2) Gibbs Free Energy Change of Adsorption (ΔG_{ads})

From the values of Gibbs free energy values calculated and presented in table 3, it can be seen that all the values are negative. This indicates that the adsorption process of the inhibitor molecules on the aluminum surface is a spontaneous process. A second look at the values will reveal that the values lie between -8.375KJ/mol and -13.007KJ/mol. ΔG values of up to -20KJ/mol are consisted with electrostatic interaction between the Inhibitor molecules and the metal surface which is termed as physisorption, while that of up to -40KJ/mol leads to chemisorption interaction (Ayuba et al., 2014).

This shows that the adsorption of Citrus aurantifolia leaves extract acting as the inhibitor obeys physisorption adsorption.

3) Enthalpy Change (ΔH)

The enthalpy change data as reported in table 4 shows the variation of enthalpy change with Inhibitor concentration. The values are decreasing (becoming more negative) with increasing Inhibitor concentration. So also, the result shows how Enthalpy change also decrease with increasing temperature.

The negative values of the enthalpy change tell the exothermic behavior of the adsorption process. The behavior can be explained base on the fact that increasing temperature can lead to the desorption of some of the adsorbed molecules from the aluminum surface (Deng and Li, 2012).

V. CONCLUSION

Citrus aurantifolia leaves extracted in ethanol was found to have the inhibition effect against aluminum corrosion in HCl acid by adsorption of the molecules on the metal surface through a physical adsorption. SEM study can also be used to prove the inhibition effect of this plant extract.

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